

Mobile Technologies applied to protect victims of a crime within the EU Area of Justice: RightsApp for e-Justice

D5.1 Dissemination package

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ACRONYMS LIST:

EU: European Union

IDT: Institute of Law and Technology

ISS: International Support Service, former International Welcome Point (IWP)

UAB: Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document provides the dissemination package for the RightsApp project. It includes a description and some figures of:

- The website of the RightsApp project (previously introduced in RightsApp Deliverable D1.3: “Project website”¹).
- Rollup
- Leaflet
- Sticker
- Presentation and deliverable templates
- Twitter account created for the project.

¹ Available at: <https://zenodo.org/record/1327344>

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1 INTRODUCTION

The deliverable introduces the dissemination package for the RightsApp project. Therefore, this document is structured as follows: Section 2 contains the materials for the dissemination package such as the project website, the rollup, the leaflet, the sticker and the templates for presentations and deliverables; Section 3 shows the Social Media channel aimed at disseminating project's results.

This document is an open document. It means that it can be updated throughout the course of the project. For instance, new versions of the leaflet could be produced containing achievements of the project. Thus, this deliverable contains a revision log table. When relevant updates occur, the revision log table will reflect the update, the date of the new revision, and the author.

2 MATERIALS

This Section contains the materials that will be used in the dissemination planned activities within the lifespan of the RightsApp project.

2.1 Website

Figure 1 shows the front page of the project’s website. The RightsApp Deliverable D1.3: “Project website” shows with more detail the project home page, thus, in this deliverable only the show page is displayed. For further information see: <https://zenodo.org/record/1327344>.

Figure 1: RightsApp project website front page

2.2 Rollup

This Section shows the rollup specifically designed for the planned dissemination activities within the RightsApp project. Figure 2 depicts the rollup that contains:

- The link to the RightsApp project's home page
- The RightsApp logo and the complete name of the project
- A QR code that links to the RightsApp project's website
- The logos of the participants in the project: Institute of Law and Technology (IDT), UAB Faculty of Law, International Support Service (ISS), formerly International Welcome Point, and the Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (UAB).
- Information on EU funding.

Figure 2: RightsApp project rollup

2.3 Leaflet

This Section provides the leaflet of the RightsApp project which contains two sides that offer different information. The first side includes:

- The logo, short and full name of the project
- A picture representing some of the compatibilities and features that the project enables: assistance, information, navigation to relevant entities and the European target of the project.
- Information on EU funding
- The logo of the UAB

The second side of the leaflet shows:

- A background description of the project
- The main objective of the project
- Some relevant information about the project
 - Duration
 - Programme
 - Reference of the Grant Agreement
 - The coordination institution
 - How to reach the team and how to follow the achievements of the project

Figure 3: RightsApp project leaflet

2.4 Sticker

Figure 4 depicts the sticker of the RightsApp project that shows basic information about the project. It contains:

- Information on EU funding

- The logo, short and full name of the project
- The link to the project’s website
- The contact details for the e-mail and twitter account
- A QR code that links to the RightsApp project’s website

Figure 4: RightsApp project sticker

2.5 Templates

This section shows the deliverable and presentation templates for the RightsApp project.

2.5.1 Deliverables template

Figure 5 shows the first part of deliverable template for the RightsApp project. This first part contains:

- Logo, full, and short name of the project
- Some details about the project such as, among others, the funding scheme, project’s coordinator, deliverable responsible author and contributor authors, starting date and duration
- Information on EU funding
- Reviews log table, acronyms list, and executive summary

Figure 5: RightsApp deliverable template part 1/3

Figure 6 shows the second part of the deliverable that contains:

- Table of contents of the deliverable
- The list of figures and tables
- The sections of the deliverable

Figure 6: RightsApp deliverable template part 2/3

Finally, Figure 7 provides the last part of the deliverable template:

- An example of a figure and table for the document
- The references section, if needed
- The Annexes section, if needed

Figure 7: RightsApp deliverable template part 3/3

2.5.2 Presentation template

This section addresses the presentation template for the RightsApp project. This template contains:

- First slide, which shows the full name and logo of the project (Figure 8, left)
- Presentation title, speaker name, location and date (Figure 8, left)
- Information on EU funding (Figure 8, left)
- Slide for the section heading (Figure 8, right)
- Slide with title and various levels of texts (Figure 9, left)

- The last slide, which contains the contact details for the project and the logos of the participant entities (Figure 9, right)

Figure 8: RightsApp presentation template part 1/2

Figure 9: RightsApp presentation template part 2/2

3 SOCIAL MEDIA

The RightsApp project social network strategy will rely on two main pillars. The first is a twitter account, introduced in Section 3.1, which is a social network focused on a general and diversified nature of topics. Thus, the twitter account will be used to disseminate project achievements and events in order to reach key end-users and stakeholders, as well as EU citizens. The second pillar consists of the SlideShare account presented in Section 3.2. This account is focused on the sharing of presentations and visual material. It is mainly addressed to an academic audience (i) enabling the definition of a considerable set of keywords and consistent descriptions of each audio-visual material, (ii) easing the search of specific content and, consequently, (iii) increasing the degree of expert acquaintance.

In order to build and increase the audience levels of the RightsApp social media channels, engaging target end-users and relevant stakeholders, the following actions will be taken:

- Promotion through RightsApp social media channels
- Promotion through participant entities’ social media channels
- Follow/Like social media accounts from other related projects and request them to follow/like RightsApp
- Use of relevant hashtags

3.1 Twitter

At present, Twitter is a core social network for research, engagement and awareness. Twitter has over 313 million monthly users and, according to Twitter statistics², the top reason why people visit Twitter is to “discover something new and interesting”. Thus, Twitter has become a key factor in the dissemination strategy for the RightsApp project, aiming at building brand and project momentum, and collecting feedback from researchers, stakeholders, potential consumers, and EU citizens.

RightsApp has set up a Twitter account https://twitter.com/p_rightsapp with the user name: @p_rightsapp. In this account, the project will share results, meetings, conferences, public events and, to sum it up, all its relevant achievements and events. In addition, the Twitter account enables comments and feedback from researchers and stakeholders. Figure 10 shows a screenshot of the RightsApp account on Twitter.

Figure 10: RightsApp twitter account

² <https://business.twitter.com/en/video-on-twitter.html>

3.2 SlideShare

This tool, which is associated with LinkedIn, will be used to share information about the project using presentations, infographics, documents, and videos. The main goal of this tool is to increase audience awareness levels and to spread out the project results and achievements. SlideShare also allows to define a keyword set that facilitates presentations to interested users of the platform.